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Quantum Mirror as a Vortex

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ABSTRACT: Continuing the discussion on the possibility of existence of a quantum mirror of spacetime in the form of each particle we attribute this effect to its spherical vorticity due to spin

KEYWORDS: quantum mirror, spherical vorticity, particle spin, spacetime vortex, five dimensions, magnetic monopoles, hidden variables

INTRODUCTION

In our investigations we claim that left intact the quantum system performs cycles in a P V diagram with a coefficient of efficiency. Time does not flow. When a photon hits the electron or the system heat is exchanged and time flows together with entropy. Energy flows from a fifth dimension creating the illusion of monopole antimonopole formation. Spin plays a central role in this.

Main part

We shall start with a question.

Have you ever wondered why we picture spin as a vector while it is not a three dimensional vector? It represent the indices of a watch. In five dimensions a ring is rotating. This is equivalent to a hypersphere of simultaneity in four dimensions.

Spin is the true measure of acceleration which brings events in spacetime and a phenomenal appearance of magnetic South and North pole.

The angles with which the ring in five dimensions is turning are perceived as solid angles in our world. The point particle which is a quantum mirror is also a vortex. That way it can stick to one place

The very fact that spin has more than one projection to the axes together with the fact that they can not be measured simultaneously suggests the idea of the particle having a spherical vortex of spacetime form.

In German the word for time is Zeit. It is the Z axis which is measuring time. Time is formed each time a pair of magnetic monopoles antimonopoles form pointing North (end) and South (beginning)

If we come to concentrate on the yin yang symbol we may observe a ring rotating with the S in the middle which is the waveform. It is a wave of polarization. It also accounts for Spin. If we turn the yin yang fast enough the grey shadow will be formed. It is the shadow in our three dimensional world of procedures taking place in the fifth dimension. This is what the hat upon the operator creates. A measurable effect in our world. Therefore this polarization wave is also a wave of turbulence diffusion of the spacetime.

Turbulence creates negative pressure. This is the minus sign in the h bar symbol. This wave is also a wave of density and therefore volume vibrations. This is what the existence of longitudinal photons foresee together with the assumed existence of magnetic monopoles.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions reached are not decisive yet but a lot of mathematical evidence in the reference section supports that the model is stable. We believe there are hidden variables in quantum mechanics but there must be continuation of this effort by other scientists.

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